

D6.3 5G-IANA micro-projects integration report

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Control sheet

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Executive Summary

Deliverable 6.3 includes the strategy of the 5G-IANA project in order to attract, engage, and support external SMEs, referred to as third party experimenters, so that they can run their experiments leveraging the Automotive Open Experimental Platform (AOEP).

This engagement plan includes five distinct phases, namely research and preparation of similar activities from previous projects, promotion of the 5G-IANA platform and Open Call objectives, launching of the Open Call and soliciting of applications, followed by the actual pre-testing and validation activities of the selected SMEs.

The first project Open Call was launched in February 2023, and closed on June 2023, receiving five applications. So far, one SME has successfully concluded their experiment. The second project Open Call is expected to be launched in January 2024.

This deliverable describes the scope and terms of the Open Calls, the way in which interested SMEs can apply, as well as describes the procedure of SME selection and potential funding. References to useful manuals at the disposal of third parties are provided (i.e., a guide for applicants, a technical manual, and a manual describing the available network applications and atomic components of the project).

The outcomes of the first Open Call are also described, commenting also on the challenges and prohibiting factors of SME engagement.

The deliverable concludes with an Appendix that contains the report of the experiment conducted by Link Robotics, following their experimentation in NOKIA testbed in November 2023, as well as the exact application form requested to be completed by the interested SMEs.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 5G-IANA concept and approach

5G-IANA aims at providing an open 5G experimentation platform, on top of which third-party experimenters, i.e., SMEs in the automotive vertical sector will have the opportunity to develop, deploy and test their services. The provided automotive Open Experimentation Platform (AOEP) is a set of hardware and software resources that provides the computational and communication/transport infrastructure as well as the management and orchestration components, coupled with an enhanced network application Toolkit tailored to the automotive sector, for simplifying the design and onboarding of new network applications. 5G-IANA exposes to experimenters secured and standardized Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) for facilitating all the different steps towards the production stage of a new service. 5G-IANA targets different virtualization technologies integrating different Management and Orchestration (MANO) frameworks for enabling the deployment of end-to-end network services across different segments (vehicles, road infrastructure, Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) nodes and cloud resources). 5G-IANA network application toolkit is linked with an automotive Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) Repository including an extensive portfolio of ready-to-use and openly accessible automotive-related VNFs and network application templates, that are available for SMEs to use and develop new applications. Finally, 5G-IANA develops a Distributed Machine Learning (DML) framework, that provides functionalities for simplified management and orchestration of collections of Machine Learning (ML) service components and thus, allows ML-based applications to penetrate the automotive world, due to its inherent privacy-preserving nature. 5G-IANA will be demonstrated through seven automotive-related use cases in two 5G Stand Alone (SA) testbeds. Moving beyond technological challenges, and exploiting input from the demonstration activities, 5G-IANA will identify and validate market conditions for innovative, yet sustainable business models for the AOEP platform, supporting a long-term roadmap towards the pan-European deployment of 5G as a key advanced automotive services enabler.

1.2 Purpose of the deliverable

The objective of this deliverable is to document the strategy of the 5G-IANA project for engaging third parties, the procedure followed in this direction, as well as the results stemming from the first Open Call. The deliverable has the following structure:

Section 2 describes the phases of the third party engagement plan, together with their implementation approach.

Section 3 presents the scope of the first Open Call, and the planned procedures.

Section 4 provides the outcomes and insights gained from the first Open Call.

Section 5 provides some adjustments that are planned for the second project Open Call.

Section 6 concludes the deliverable.

Appendix 1 presents the results of the experiments of one third party that has concluded their Open Call obligations.

Appendix 2 includes the Open Call's Interest Form (application form for SMEs).

1.3 Intended audience

The dissemination level of D6.3 is 'public' (PU) and is available to members of the consortium, the European Commission (EC) Services and those external to the project. Potential applicants to the second project Open Call can find this document valuable to learn more information about the approach, the procedure, and the expected results and outcomes of this Open Call.

2. ENGAGEMENT PLAN FOR THIRD PARTIES – FIRST OPEN CALL

The engagement of third parties with the 5G-IANA platform is crucial for achieving a high impact of the project. In order to increase the participation of third parties to the activities of the project, an engagement plan has been created for the first project Open Call. The plan is comprised of different phases that align with the technical work that is being implemented in the other WPs of the project. This section presents more details about the engagement plan (A brief version of this plan is also included in D5.1, together with the overall project workplan).

Initially, desk research has been performed in order to identify best practices regarding the engagement activities that have been performed by other projects. Based on the collected information and discussions among the partners of the 5G-IANA consortium, the engagement plan and the associated phases that are described in this section was drafted. Furthermore, the detailed timeline for the third-party engagement plan has been aligned to the overall development, integration, and validation workplan of the project. The objective of the engagement plan is to attract third parties in order to experiment during the Open Calls that the project organizes. Two phases of the Open Call have been planned that are aligned with the development cycles of the project. The timeline is presented in Figure 1 and is further analysed below.

Figure 1: Timeline of the engagement plan in alignment with the project workplan

The engagement plan is divided in the following phases (Figure 2):

Figure 2: Open Call 1 phases

- **Research and preparation:** includes the review of the engagement activities performed by other projects that have implemented Open Calls and the preparation of the necessary material for the upcoming phases. This phase started on M15 and was concluded on M19; it will run again just before the second Open Call to provide any updates that have been identified from the first phase of the Open call.
- **Promotion:** during that phase the capabilities of the 5G-IANA platform are being communicated to potentially interested third parties, while the preparation of material such as presentations, info days and webinars are organised. The activities of this phase officially kicked off on M19 and they will last until the end of the project but will be more intense just before the launching of the Open Calls (M19-M21) and M29 to M32.
- **Open call:** during this phase external parties are requested to submit their proposals regarding the experiments that they would be interested in running on the 5G-IANA platform. This phase is also completed in two cycles: M21-M24 and M32 to M35. During the last month of the Open Call (for each of the cycles) the selection process is initiated.
- **Pre-testing:** it includes closer collaboration between the selected third parties and the 5G-IANA consortium, while training activities are also foreseen to take place in this phase. The duration of this phase is two months for the first cycle, (M25-M26) while during the second cycle it has been merged with the next phase (as justified in Section 5).
- **Validation and report:** the developed solutions from third parties are being validated using the same procedures that are defined for the internal project use cases. This phase has a duration of four months for the first cycle (M27-M30) and five months for

the second cycle, after being merged with the pre-testing phase (M36-M40). The last weeks (depicted as a whole month in Figure 1) of this phase are allocated to the reporting of the performed activities.

In the following sections, more details are provided for each of the activities that take place in each of the phases of the engagement plan.

2.1 Research and preparation

The objective of this phase is to identify all the required material that needs to be prepared for the successful implementation of the upcoming phases of the engagement plan. An additional activity is to identify possible third parties that might be interested in participating at the Open Call. Towards that direction, each of the partners of the 5G-IANA consortium was asked to provide their input in order to compile an initial list of SMEs. In addition, an e-mail was drafted with basic information about the project and the Open Call to be circulated during the promotion phase to the network of each partner, to the different lists of 5GPPP and 6G-IA, the other projects of ICT-41 call, the 5GAA and ERTICO, among others.

The activities that should be completed before the Open Call include the definition of both the technical and managerial procedures that must be followed (in collaboration with the other WPs), to decide on the eligibility criteria and the evaluation procedure. Some indicative material that has been prepared and used during the promotion phase includes the following information:

- List of all atomic components (AFs/NFs) and network applications that are available
- The rules and procedures for third-party experimentation
- Technical manual (user guide)
- Information about the technical support
- Template in which third parties can declare their interest
- Creation of webinars and videos
- Preparation of Info Day material (to announce the Open Call)
- Legal documents that are required for accessing the platform.

Part of this material has been organised in a downloadable “Guide for applicants” document, while other dedicated manuals are provided as well (more details are available at Section 2.3).

2.2 Promotion

The promotion phase of the engagement plan started on M19. WP7 has been actively involved in the “third-party workplan” by leading and executing promotional activities. The project’s Communication management has defined an approach and communication strategy specifically for this activity.

The first action on this strategy has been the creation of a particular section on the project’s website aiming to attract third parties (Figure 3). The website is the main tool for advertising as well as for soliciting the interest regarding the two Open Calls to third parties. This section provides visitors with key information about the project, the platform, the instructions to get involved as well as all technical and legal details required for their involvement.

Figure 3: Website section devoted to third parties

This communication strategy defines as well concrete communication and promotional activities oriented to the promotion of the Open Calls. These activities are being implemented in three phases:

- **Phase 1: announcement of the Open Call and preliminary communication | Cycle A (M19-M21), Cycle B (M29-M32)**

The main objective of this phase is to approach the SMEs ecosystem targeted through the project’s communication channels (press releases, website, social media, newsletters, promotional materials) and the partners’ own communication channels and networks (internal & external contacts, website, social media, mailing lists and different working groups).

The main activity of the Phase 1 has been the announcement of the Open Call process in February 2023. Additionally, an intense promotional e-mail campaign has been also foreseen prior to the announcement of the Open Call - to target groups (T1.4), SMEs identified by the consortium, other projects, partner's networks, etc.

- **Phase 2 : main Open Call communication | Cycle A (M21-M24), Cycle B (M32-M35)**

The core activity of this second phase is the intense promotion of the Open Call process for attracting SME applicants. This is done through active website and social media campaigns from a project level, extensive use of internal and external communication channels and networks of all partners, and liaison activities with ICT-41 projects and other associations (5G-PPP/5G-IA and WGs, 5G-PPP Comms, etc.). The project also organised one "Info Day" about the first Open Call and the release of promotional materials specifically created for the Open Call.

- **Phase 3: follow-up communication | Cycle A (M25-M30), Cycle B (M35-M40)**

The scope of this phase is to follow up Open Call communication for making known in public the Open Call results and achievements (winners, results and activities/events). Activities during this phase are executed through active website and social media campaigns from a project level, as well as press releases and Open Call events. Again, the partner's communication channels are being used for promotion as well when relevant.

All the channels used for promotion are presented at Figure 4.

A document describing the approach and the Open Call communication strategy has been released to the consortium internally with the aim of aligning the efforts and activities defined under the different phases. Sample texts for mailing, posts and news announcements and campaigns have also been included. The information on this document will be regularly monitored and updated by the project's Communication leader in order to provide the latest information and guidelines for the prompt and efficient communication of 5G-IANA's Open Calls.

A detailed plan of the Open Calls promotion activities and communication phases (scope, channels, activities) has been provided in D7.3 - Communication strategy and plan V2 (M21).

Figure 4: Channels used for promotion

2.3 Open call

The 5G-IANA Open Calls will take place in two phases (cycles): Cycle A (M21-M24) and Cycle B (M32-M35). The announcements of these Open Calls coincide with the final phases of the integration processes in the two development cycles, and thus, they follow the release of the two versions of the 5G-IANA platform.

Audience: The Open Calls are targeted to SMEs, outside of the consortium of the project; moreover, it will be ensured that they are not addressed to any SMEs with conflicts of interest with the consortium members. Moreover, the focus will be on SMEs not currently participating in other ICT-41 projects.

Stages: Each Open Call consists of two stages: a) the application stage, and b) the evaluation (selection) stage.

During the **application stage**, the Open Call will be intensely promoted as presented in the previous section. The goal will be twofold: not only to massively reach out to special groups of potential interest (e.g., 5GAA, Info Day, etc.), but also to reach out in a more personalised way to specific SMEs that the partners have identified. The consortium has collected a list of 27 SMEs¹ that may have a potential interest in experimenting with the 5G-IANA platform. Also, a few SMEs have reached out on their own, following the promotional campaign. More targeted and personal communication has been initiated with a few of these SMEs (in the context of both the first and second Open Call), so that through such interactions, the 5G-IANA partners will be in the position to clearly understand the needs of such SMEs and incentivise them to be actively engaged. Their needs will be discussed in terms of the applicability of current or potential future services/AFs/NFs/network applications that they would find value in onboarding on the 5G-IANA platform or in testing using 5G, and to hopefully engage them to apply to the Open Call.

During the **evaluation stage**, the goal is to process all the received applications and evaluate them. A clear set of eligibility criteria will be used so that all applications can be graded and prioritised. We have formed an Evaluation Committee as well, composed of key 5G-IANA members as well as members of our External Advisory Board. As an example, prioritization will be given to SMEs that do not have a research/academia profile (i.e., pure industrial SMEs) - subject however to the amount of interest that we will receive -, to SMEs that use the innovative platform and 5G capabilities “the best”, and to SMEs that bring the highest value by the proposed service or product for the final user. Following this stage, the administrative/legal arrangements for experimenting on the testbeds will start.

Produced material: To support the Open Calls, 5G-IANA is in the process of preparing the following material. This will be used for the purposes of a) publishing the Open Calls, b) preparing the logistics behind the Open Calls, c) helping the applicants/potential experimenters understand the capabilities of the 5G-IANA platform, supporting them if selected, and facilitating them in raising any questions:

Publishing:

¹ Specifically, we are collecting the following information: SME name, Website, Area of expertise, Contact information, How could they benefit from 5G-IANA, How did you find this SME?, Are they involved in research projects? If yes, explain: ICT/etc.?, Response/status, Conflict of Interest (Y/N)

- A [Guide for Applicants](#) document has been prepared, presenting the administrative procedure with regard to the Open Calls, i.e., a document that contains all useful information for the submission of a proposal from third parties (Figure 5). The content of this document is the following:
 - **Scope and terms of the Open Call:** objectives, anticipated gains, eligibility criteria
 - **Project overview:** terminology, project concept, platform capabilities, testbeds
 - **How to apply:** application form, submission procedure, helpful material
 - **After the application - what to expect:** eligibility and feasibility check, logistics, pre-testing, experimentation, mentoring, reporting
 - **Selection of award winners:** assessment criteria, awards details

The content of this document that was released with the first Open Call is presented in Section 3.

Figure 5: Guide for applicants cover page

- The recording of the Info Day webinar: Promotion of the 5G-IANA AOEP Release 1, explaining the offered capabilities/facilities and reusable functionalities (e.g.,

NFs/AFs), description of repositories (network application toolkit), degrees of freedom given to the experimenters, benefits from using the platform, etc.

Logistics:

- Rules and procedures for third parties' experimentation (to help ensure that any required conditions are met for the admission of third parties to the project testbeds). Also, this includes the administrative procedure for the distribution of funding to the third parties. Thus, legal documents (contracts) that will need to be signed between the third party experimenter and ICCS/other partner for accessing the testbeds are required.

Supporting:

- [Technical manual / platform user guide](#) (Figure 6). This manual will be used in conjunction with the Guide for Applicants document but includes more technical details. This manual can be a useful tool to help the experimenters better understand how different use cases or network applications can be implemented, onboarded and run on the 5G-IANA platform (as a guide/example to develop their own UCs). Based on the expertise of the third parties, this manual can be used partially or fully by them.

Figure 6: Technical manual cover page

Some examples of the content included is:

- Definitions
- AF/NF development & packaging
- AF/NF uploading
- Network application composition: Entering the web platform, registration of individual AFs/NFs, network application graph composition & registration, onboarding, network application deployment
- Network application starter kit
- [5G-IANA Application Functions, Network Functions, and Network Applications manual](#): Regarding the AFs/NFs (atomic components) provided by the project, an already available manual with their description has been provided (Description, Input required, Output provided, Examples of communicating AFs/NFs), so that third parties can understand how they could combine their proprietary functions with 5G-IANA's AFs/NFs, in order to form new network applications. This manual consists of the description of a plethora of atomic components and network applications, in the format shown in Figure 7, for a characteristic example.

QoS Prediction					
Name	QoS Prediction	Code	CAF-26 B-VNF30	Domain	OBU
Description	This VNF is based on the trained Distributed ML model present at the Edge node.				
Comments	An LSTM prediction model is trained on each edge node and aggregated at the DML server. This aggregated global model is then transmitted to all the Edge nodes for training and inference.				
Input required	ML model, ML-specific dataset (Spatial position and time for QoS prediction)				
Output provided	Predicted QoS (based on ML model latency or rate) value				
Examples of communicating VNFs	This VNF communicates with the AggNode VNF to acquire a trained ML model and using (cleaned) datasets from the Preprocessing VNF produces predictions.				

Figure 7: Example of a virtual function (atomic component)

- Technical support: this includes a simple ticketing system using Trello, so that when users send an e-mail to helpdesk@5g-iana.eu, this will be automatically onboarded on the Trello ticketing workspace, where it will be monitored and resolved.

- Business model guidance: workshops can be organised to assist third parties to develop their business plan and thus speed up the process of getting their results closer to the market.

2.4 Pre-testing

The pre-testing phase marks the initiation of the overall third party experimentation phase. The main goal in this phase is to define in detail the targets of the selected third party contributions and go through a series of functional tests in order to verify the interoperability of the solution to the platform and other linked network application components. In turn, this will provide to the involved third party an understanding of the 5G-IANA platform environment, and to the associated 5G-IANA partner(s) an understanding of the targeted network application capabilities. This phase is considered as a preparation phase for the validation and testing phase that follows. Any potential misalignments or updates are intended to be identified and corrected in this phase or identify functional alternatives.

The duration of the pre-testing phase during the first Open Call is two months and includes the following activities:

- The extraction of a detailed validation plan for the third party involvement with clear deployment and testing targets, as well as identification of the required 5G-IANA infrastructure requirements.
- The familiarisation of the third party with the 5G-IANA platform capabilities and additional network application components that may be linked or reused.
- The examination of the network application component(s) to fulfil the deployment requirements (e.g., in terms of exposed and required parameters, compatibility with Kubernetes structure, exposed interfaces and interconnection with targeted end user hardware, etc.).
- The functional pre-testing of the proposed network application, (or network application component extending an existing network application) including at least,
 - the correct editing of the required parameters through the front-end interface,
 - the registration of the offered network application component(s) to the catalogue,
 - the deployment of the targeted network application within the SW testing environment, showing the proper creation of slice intent and the slice response,

- the evaluation of the proper communication between linked network application components required for the overall validation and testing,
- identification of any potential changes or updates that may be required.

2.5 Validation and reporting

For the validation of the services that will be run and validated on the 5G-IANA platform the same methodologies as for the internal use cases will be used. WP5 (5G-enabled Automotive network applications validation and demonstration) has defined the methodologies to be used to evaluate the capabilities of the 5G-IANA architecture in order to support and develop new, advanced automotive-related services as defined and to be deployed in the use cases. WP5 has already defined research questions and the metrics/KPIs that will be used for the validation of the components/mechanisms developed and used in the 5G-IANA platform including definition of suitable acceptance criteria per component/mechanism. The result of this work is available in deliverable D5.1 (Initial validation KPIs and metrics). Moreover, the definition of the exact validation methodology to be used has been reported in deliverable D5.2 (Validation methodology). In terms of engagement of third parties through WP5 activities, the definition of open interfaces to monitor and operate use cases enabling automated testing and the preparation and deployment of a testing framework to automate and homogenize the use case validation will lead to a 5G-IANA testing toolkit. This testing toolkit will offer a perfect sandbox environment as an essential asset to attract third party experimenters allowing them to use, extend, and test 5G-IANA components thus permitting the development of new 5G-based services in an efficient manner ensuring an accelerated time-to-market for new products.

The validation phase ends with the creation of the reports describing the activities that have been performed during the validation phase. A questionnaire and report will be shared in order to collect feedback from the experimenters. Also, the experimenters will be encouraged to take videos and photos, so as to prepare a video clip and advertise it through 5G-IANA channels. The validation phase concludes with the announcement of the winners of the awards.

3. FIRST OPEN CALL

The first Open Call was launched on 20 February 2023 (Figure 8). Below is the information that has been provided to the public, as the means to inform and attract potential third party experimenters. This information is part of the Guide for Applicants document.

The graphic is a vertical rectangular poster with a dark blue background. At the top left is the 5G IANA logo. At the top right is the European Union flag. The main title 'OPEN CALL RELEASED!' is in large, bold, yellow and white text. Below this, a white megaphone icon is followed by the text 'Calling SMEs and start-ups to run their automotive network applications on top of the platform provided by 5G-IANA project, making use of 5G connectivity!' with a small 5G signal icon. The deadline 'Applications are open until: 22 May 2023, 05:00:00 PM CEST' is in yellow text. Below that, the website 'Visit 5g-iana.eu/open-call for more information' is in white text. A yellow box contains the text 'For any inquiries, contact us at: open-call@5g-iana.eu'. At the bottom left, there are social media icons for Twitter, LinkedIn, and a website icon, with their respective links: 'twitter.com/IANA_5G', 'linkedin.com/company/5g-iana', and '5g-iana.eu'. The bottom right corner features a photograph of a winding road through a landscape.

Figure 8: Announcement of the first Open Call

3.1 Scope and Terms of the Open Call

3.1.1 General objectives

The project 5G-IANA, funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016427, organises an Open Call for the involvement and engagement of “third parties” with the 5G-IANA “Automotive Open Experimental Platform (AOEP)”.

The intended audience of this Open Call is any legal entity in the form of a Small and Medium-sized Enterprise (SME / start-up), which is working with the concept of network applications in the automotive vertical, and which is already developing or is willing to develop a product or service or functionality that leverages 5G capabilities through the 5G-IANA platform. The scope of this Open Call is to help SMEs develop and integrate their innovative idea using the 5G-IANA platform, facilitating in parallel the developed Repository of Virtual Network Functions (VNFs).

The profile of the SME that may be suitable for experimentation on the 5G-IANA platform can be one of the following (not an exhaustive list):

- **Service Creators:** all types of service creation entities such as software developers.
- **Service Providers:** who are responsible for providing a service to end users (for example Intelligent Driving, HD maps, etc.).
- **Application and Network Functions Developers:** who develop Virtual Network Functions (VNFs), i.e., Application Functions (AFs) and/or Network Functions (NFs) that can be used as building blocks for creating network applications.
- **Application and Network Functions Providers:** who are responsible for providing AFs and NFs to be on-boarded through the functionalities provided by the 5G-IANA platform.
- **Network Application Developers:** who are responsible for the development of Network Applications (network applications).
- **Network Application Providers:** who provide the network applications either to end users or service creators/providers.

Note that, an SME may well hold more than one of these roles.

3.1.2 Anticipated gains by participating in the Open Call

The participants of the Open Call will reap the following benefits offered by 5G-IANA:

- Gain access to a “canvas” to develop new functions and services in the automotive 5G landscape;
- Test and validate their existing or new services or products or scenarios in real-time using 5G connectivity;
- Gain access to real-life 5G resources (vehicles, OBUs, RSUs, EDGE/MEC Server(s));
- Get continuous mentorship and support from network and automotive experts;
- Explore/Build new business models within the 5G ecosystem;
- Gain visibility towards the EU, the 5G community and the automotive community.

Specifically, the offerings to the selected participants by 5G-IANA will be:

- Access to the “AOEP” platform to develop, deploy and test their services;
- A catalogue of available virtual Application and Network Functions (AFs/NFs, approx. 70), and Network Applications (network applications) (approx. 26);
- Tools to prepare and onboard their own AFs, NFs or network applications on the 5G-IANA platform;
- Indicative examples and experience regarding the actual deployment of use cases of the 5G-IANA consortium into the platform, i.e.: automotive-related services in the hazard-notification, infotainment, vehicle movement or even vertical-agnostic domain;
- Remote accessibility to 5G resources (through NOKIA’s site in the City of Ulm, Germany / Telecom Slovenia’s site in Ljubljana);
- Accessibility to On-Board Unit (OBU) / Road-Side Unit (RSU) resources through the AOEP platform and experimentation potential using real vehicles;
- Support to Machine Learning (ML)-oriented services (if needed), through our Distributed Machine Learning framework;
- Technical support material in the form of a technical manual, webinars and other published material;
- Mentorship, training, technical assistance and support;
- Business model mentoring;
- Access to 5G-IANA project’s network of professionals, media, and partners;
- Funding, based on an awarding scheme (*this awarding scheme applies to the first Open Call*).

3.1.3 Eligibility criteria

The call is open to SMEs and start-ups legally established in an eligible country. Legal entities must be established in the Member States of the European Union and associated countries according to the Horizon Europe rules². An SME will be considered as such if accomplishing with the Commission Recommendation 2003/361/EC³ and the SME user guide⁴.

Only one entity per proposal is allowed (no consortia are allowed).

The applicant must be completely independent of project partners, their affiliated entities and/or their controlled companies. Institutions, organizations or other kinds of legal entities funded by or otherwise affiliated with a 5G-IANA partner are not eligible.

5G-IANA retains the right to discard the selected application in case one (or more) of the conditions above are not satisfied.

3.1.4 Eligible countries

Only applicants legally established and operational in any of the following countries will be eligible:

- The Member States of the European Union, including their outermost regions.
- The Overseas Countries and Territories linked to the Member States⁵.
- H2020 Associated countries: according to the updated list published by the EC⁶.

The UK applicants are eligible under the conditions set by the EC for H2020 participation at the time of the deadline of the call.

3.2 How to apply

This section outlines the procedures for the submission of applications to the 5G-IANA Open Call. As a summary (details are available in the following sections):

- The applicants must use original work in their proposal.
- Proposals must provide details on how they will use the 5G-IANA platform.

² https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/list-3rd-country-participation_horizon-euratom_en.pdf

³ European Commission Recommendation 2003/361/EC, 2020, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2003:124:0036:0041:en:PDF>

⁴ https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/smes/sme-definition_en

⁵ Entities from Overseas Countries and Territories (OCT) are eligible for funding under the same conditions as entities from the Member States to which the OCT in question is linked.

⁶ http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/3cpart/h2020-hi-list-ac_en.pdf

- Proposals must be written in English and submitted through the 5G-IANA website in order to be eligible (until the deadline of the Open Call).
- Incomplete proposals will not be evaluated.

3.2.1 Application form

The Application Form is online and requires filling in information regarding the following aspects (Sections) shown at Figure 9.

5G-IANA Open Call Interest Form

Last Chance

.....

<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between; align-items: center;"> + Step 1 General information </div>	
<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between; align-items: center;"> + Step 2 Ambitions and development plans </div>	
<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between; align-items: center;"> + Step 3 Experience </div>	
<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between; align-items: center;"> + Step 4 Expectations from the platform </div>	
<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between; align-items: center;"> + Step 5 Expected impact </div>	
<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between; align-items: center;"> + Step 6 Before you submit </div>	

All Open Call projects will be expected to comply with the General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR).

Send

Figure 9: Open Call Interest Form

1. **General information** about the applicant: Contact point, organization name and type, short description of business profile, country.
2. **Ambitions and development plans:** Description of service, solution, functionality or product that the applicant would like to deploy on the platform, and details about the proposed experiment on the 5G-IANA platform.
3. **Previous experience:** Prior experience with network applications'/virtual functions' development and with 5G.

4. **Expectations from the platform:** Expectations regarding the area covered by a 5G testbed, draft estimate of required resources in terms of hardware and software resources, and anticipated testbed time allocation.
5. **Expected impact:** Anticipated leverage on the 5G-IANA platform and potential impact on the applicant's business portfolio.

The previous categories are broken down into specific questions in the application form, which can be found and submitted online (<https://www.5g-iana.eu/get-involved/open-call/#form> - **Error! Reference source not found.**). All fields are mandatory to be filled in. The exact application form questions are included in the Appendix 2 for completeness.

3.2.2 Submission of applications

The online Application Form shall be completed any time after the launch of the Open Call (20 February 2023) **until 22 May 2023 (05:00:00 PM CEST)**.

The form will be deactivated on 22 May 2023 at 05:00:00 PM CEST, and thus all applications received after this time will be automatically discarded. Applicants are strongly recommended to submit their applications with a reasonable advance over the deadline, in order to ensure they are successfully delivered on time, even in case of technical or connectivity problems.

5G-IANA will send a confirmation receipt to the e-mail address applying, notifying that it has been taken into charge by the system; such confirmation does not certify that the application is complete and suitable for evaluation, but simply that the e-mail was received in time.

Note that the deadline was extended, as an effort to allow for receiving more applications, until **15 June 2023**.

3.2.3 Further information for the applicants

Applicants are invited to visit the 5G-IANA Open Call page regularly (<https://5g-iana.eu/open-call/>), in order to get the latest news about the call.

In case of specific queries on the call, applicants may write an e-mail to open-call@5g-iana.eu with the subject "Support" to receive help from the 5G-IANA Applicant Helpdesk team.

Figure 10 and Figure 11 provide a summary of the general timing of the 5G-IANA Open Call.

Figure 10: Timeline of the 5G-IANA Open Call (vertical format)

Figure 11: Timeline of the 5G-IANA Open Call (horizontal format)

Note that 5G-IANA is going to publish a second Open Call in January 2024, with the goal to invite SMEs for validation and experimentation starting in the summer of 2024. An updated Guide for Applicants will be provided to support this second phase.

3.3 After the application: what to expect

3.3.1 From Application to Experimentation

3.3.1.1 Eligibility status

After closing the application phase, all received applications will be first filtered according to their **eligibility status**, based on criteria described in Section 3.1; for all non-eligible applications, no further evaluation will take place. Extra information may be requested by the SMEs to validate their legal entity and SME characterization (i.e., to fill in documents related to the “Declaration on information on the SME qualification”, and “Declaration of Honour on exclusion criteria and absence of conflict of interest”).

3.3.1.2 Feasibility status

Remaining eligible applications will further undergo a **feasibility check**: This process will ensure that the proposed type of experiment is a) in context with the 5G-IANA project and call scope (i.e., related to the automotive vertical or relative sector that is meaningful and can be supported by the platform), b) the SME has the basic technical expertise to allow getting familiarised with the platform basics and be in the position to complete the experimentation after receiving any required training and support, and c) has developed, is developing, or plans to develop a software function/service/application/product that will leverage the 5G-IANA platform and 5G network.

The number of selected applications is not known in advance – this will be a function of a) testbed availability/capability constraints, b) predefined time window availability for pre-testing and validation phases, c) time for anticipated experimentation declared by each SME, and d) 5G-IANA resources for close mentorship and support of the experimenters.

In case the number of applications passing the feasibility check is higher than the number of experiments that can be accommodated by the 5G-IANA platform in the given timeframe, then the remaining applications will be further evaluated as in the conditions of Section 3.4.2, related to the “Excellence” criterion only.

This process will indicatively take 15 days from the closure of the submission phase; at the end of this the selected applicants will be informed via e-mail.

3.3.2 Logistics

The selected applications from the previous procedure will start the contracting phase, which will end with the official kick-off of activities.

The successful applicants will be informed by the contracting party (ICCS) and they will be put in contact with the NOKIA testbed. The stakeholders responsible for the NOKIA or Telecom Slovenia testbed, where the Open Call solutions will be deployed, may add specific clauses to the contract. Please understand that access to a 5G testbed and its resources is a delicate process that needs careful planning and must comply with its internal processes and procedures. Granted applicants will be therefore asked to sign the appropriate micro-project agreement with the involved and relevant project partners (Figure 12).

Figure 12: Micro-project agreement snapshot

3.3.3 Validation

The pre-testing phase marks the initiation of the overall experimentation phase, as explained in Section 2.4 and 2.5.

3.3.4 Mentoring and support

Close mentorship and support will be provided to the selected experimenters so that they get familiarised with the platform (pre-testing phase), but also during the validation & testing phase.

- Technical support includes a ticketing system. Users can send an e-mail to **helpdesk@5g-iana.eu**, and then this will be handled by the 5G-IANA helpdesk as soon as possible.
- Business model guidance: workshops will be organised on demand to assist SMEs, if needed and requested by them, to develop their business model and thus speed up the process of getting their results from the experimentation closer to the market.

3.3.5 Reporting

The experimentation cycle ends with the creation of a report describing the activities that have been performed during the validation phase. The information to be included in this report consists of the following sections:

- Service setup description:
 - Description of the service, including the HW components, the SW components and their logical organization into AFs/NFs, information about which Network Application was formed (if applicable), and the traffic flows realized (content, direction), etc.
- Scenario description:
 - Based on the above information, description of the test scenarios in what concerns the pre-conditions, the various steps, the validation/evaluation objectives, the related metrics.
- Assessment:
 - A statistical analysis of the measurements.
 - Feedback on the 5G-IANA platform.

3.3.6 Produced outputs

In case the produced outputs of the experiments lead to scientific publications or if they are presented in presentations or webpages, they should include an acknowledgement to 5G-IANA and the European Commission (respective logos).

3.4 Selection of award winners

3.4.1 From experimentation to award selection

After closing the experimentation and reporting phase as presented in the previous Section, all successfully conducted experiments (i.e., having successfully collaborated with 5G-IANA partners and delivered the final report) will undergo a technical/business evaluation process, aiming to determine their ranking and select the ones that will be granted a monetary award.

The evaluation process will indicatively take one month; at the end of this process the final ranking will be notified via e-mail to all applicants and be announced on the project website.

The evaluation of successful experiments will be carried out by the 5G-IANA Mentors forming an Evaluation Committee (<https://www.5g-iana.eu/get-involved/mentors/>). These Mentors are members of the Technical Management Team of the 5G-IANA consortium, as well as members of the External Advisory Board of the project. Potentially, additional partners and experts from the 5G-IANA project can be involved as additional contributors to the evaluation process, depending on the nature and amount of the submissions.

The evaluation process will be carried out in respect of principles of fairness and transparency, according to the criteria described in Chapter 3.4.2.

Please note that the Evaluation Committee could ask for additional information at any time during the evaluation process, to reach a fully informed and fair judgement.

The decision by 5G-IANA Evaluation Committee is final and the applicants/experimenters will withhold any legal action against the decision taken.

The following section thoroughly describes the assessment criteria followed in the evaluation process.

3.4.2 Assessment criteria

The following aspects will be considered and evaluated. Per category, some of the indicative criteria that will be evaluated are presented in bullet form:

Excellence:

In this aspect, some of the indicative criteria that will be evaluated are:

- Degree of innovation and differentiation of the service/product/use case;
- Soundness of the approach building on the 5G-IANA platform;
- Ambition and value of the proposed experiment.

Implementation:

- Successful completion of the experiment, as described in the application;
- Quality and effectiveness of the experimental process;
- Degree of leverage of the 5G-IANA platform, network applications and virtual functions (e.g., the usability of provided AOEP functions);
- Interoperability between the experimenters' own component(s) and the components provided by 5G-IANA;
- Exploitation of 5G capabilities/value that 5G brings to the experiment (scenario);
- Quality of the report.

Impact:

- Business/Market potential and industrial impact **for** the SME;
- Added value **to** the 5G-IANA platform and project (increased visibility, high potential etc.);
- Expected outcomes;
- Open data.

Each of the above three criteria will accord scores as per the table below.

Table 1: Experiment evaluation scoring

Evaluation	Description	Score
Fail	The experiment fails to address the criterion or cannot be assessed due to missing or incomplete information.	0
Poor	The criterion is inadequately addressed, or there are serious inherent weaknesses.	1
Fair	The experiment broadly addresses the criterion, but there are significant weaknesses.	2
Good	The experiment addresses the criterion well, but a number of shortcomings are present.	3
Very Good	The experiment addresses the criterion very well, but a small number of shortcomings are present.	4
Excellent	The experiment successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.	5

The maximum score will be 15.

Once all aspects are scored, a final ranking of the proposals will be defined, and the four winners will be selected accordingly, as described below.

3.4.3 Awards

The procedure for granting the awards will be initiated immediately after the completion of the evaluation process. There will be one award for the first Open Call as follows:

- The experimenter with the highest ranking of the Open Call 1 will receive 15.000 euros (to be announced in January 2024).
- The second Open Call will follow a funding scheme, i.e., it will not be based on an award basis. 100000 euros will be allocated for the Open Call.

All legal and formal procedures will be followed in order to pay the awards to the winners.

For any enquiries regarding the Open Call, the e-mail **open-call@5g-iana.eu** has been created.

4. REPORT OF THE FIRST OPEN CALL RESULTS

4.1 Implementation of the first Open Call

In order to launch and run the Open Call, we have followed specific sequential steps, that map to the phases reported in Section 2. These specific practical steps are graphically depicted in the timeline below (Figure 13).

Figure 13: Open Call implementation timeline

4.2 Applications to the first Open Call

We have received five applications during the first Open Call. The names of the SMEs that have not completed their experiments (for the reasons presented below) are anonymised.

1. Application from Link Robotics: They have successfully validated their experiment. Actual development and integration efforts with this SME started at the end of August. Link Robotics managed to conclude their experiment at NOKIA, in the City of Ulm, between 14/11/23-17/11/23, with physical presence. The report of their experiment is included in the Appendix.
2. Application from SME-1: Following the acceptance of their application, and some preliminary discussions, SME-1 withdrew their interest in the Open Call.
3. Application from SME-2: Regular discussions with this SME took place, and a thorough plan for their experiment and specific scenarios were drafted. Even though this SME showed great interest in this activity, they had to freeze all activities due to the war in Israel. We plan to approach them again in the context of the second Open Call.
4. Application from SME-3: This SME has not been able to proceed so far, due to funding problems. However, these problems seem to have been surpassed. Therefore, we plan to approach them in the context of the second Open Call.
5. Application from SME-4: This SME's experiment is currently ongoing. We expect that their experiment will be finalised before the end of January.

4.3 Types of experiments

In this section, we provide some general information about the types of experiments that were submitted in the project's Open Call interest forms.

- A Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) mitigation platform on top of the 5G network and 5G-IANA platform in order to implement the DDoS as a native 5G application.
- A demonstration on an urban scenario, with real road traffic and pedestrians using a Real-Time Kinematic (RTK) service which consists of a stationary RTK base station sending Real Time Correction Messages (RTCM) data over 5G network.
- Testing of a core intelligent element for next-generation traffic management that provides active, local, and dynamic driving guidance to specific vehicles on the 5G network to test effective latency and bit rate.
- Integration of a high-precision GNSS receiver and synthetic radar in the 5G network.
- Use of 5G-IANA platform to collect field data, process them on edge and cloud resources as applicable, establish a geo-referenced map of interest areas, generate an action plan and navigation plan, and coordinate actions of ground and aerial vehicles based on them.

4.4 Prohibiting factors

We have reached the conclusion that engaging SMEs has been very challenging. The main reasons that SMEs have been hesitant to apply, based on their feedback, have been:

- Scarce resources and other business priorities prevent some SMEs from investing time in this type of activity.
- Some SMEs are skeptical as to whether they can fit the development efforts of network applications-based products.
- Another reason has been the lack of national funding to help support such an activity.
- In some experiments dozens of vehicles would be needed for tests, which are not available by the project.
- Some SMEs mentioned that 4G seems to be enough to support their specific use case.
- Another reason was that higher funding (award) would be anticipated.
- In terms of start-ups applying to the Open Call, we received feedback that start-ups resources are often in flux and they cannot guarantee to keep up with deadlines and commit resources. Sometimes there are new opportunities or problems and all efforts shift there unexpectedly.

- Other parties mentioned that they we would like to experiment with the equipment (HW and SW) in a 5G testbed, meaning that they would need to physically travel to one of the testbeds, but the budget in the form of award does not provide enough guarantees of being funded.

5. ADJUSTMENTS FOR THE SECOND OPEN CALL

The 2nd Open Call will consist of 3 phases, explained below. The timeline is depicted in Figure 14, and is explained in more detail next.

Figure 14: Open Call 2 timeline

1. PROMOTION PHASE

During this phase, the offerings of the 5G-IANA platform will be communicated to third parties, similar to Open Call 1. Promotion has been ongoing ever since the release of the 1st Open Call and will continue more intensively after the official launch of the 2nd Open Call in M32 (January 2024).

2. OPEN CALL PHASE

During this phase, external parties will be requested to submit their proposals regarding the experiments that they want to run exploiting the two project testbeds of the 5G-IANA platform. We plan to announce the 2nd Open Call in January. This announcement will provide all the required information to the third parties, so that they can confidently apply to the Open Call. The material that will be provided through our website (<https://www.5g-iana.eu/get-involved/>) is the following:

- An updated Guide for Applicants, that describes the new time plan, the updated funding scheme, the phases presented here, the updated helpful material, etc.

- An updated Technical Manual that provides information for various levels of third party experts.
- An updated “Atomic components / Network applications” manual that groups AFs, NFs and network applications by functionalities and provides a navigation tool.

The Open Call will accept applications for a period of approx. 3.5 months, i.e., until M35 (April 2024).

3. PRE-TESTING, VALIDATION and REPORT PHASE

This is a 6-month phase. The announcement of the winning applications will be done in early M36 (May 2023), immediately inviting the selected third parties to start discussions with the consortium’s Mentors, so as to design their end-to-end experiments. The experiments from third parties will be validated at the testbed of their preference (NOKIA or Telecom Slovenia). At the end of the validation, one report will be requested by the third parties. It is noted that the plan foresees an one-month buffer until the end of the project, which may be used to absorb any delays if needed.

Note that during the first Open Call, the pre-testing and validation phases were distinct, with specific timelines for each one, while in Open Call 2 they are joint. Experience has shown that the limits between these two activities are blurred and highly depend on the SMEs’ responsiveness as well as on the type of experiment; thus, as long as one third party has completed the preliminary experiment design and plan (pre-testing stage), they can immediately proceed with the validation. This dynamicity is expected to make the whole validation process more flexible and faster.

4. Funding scheme

The available funding for the second Open Call will be **100000** euros.

For the SMEs that have applied and have been selected to participate in the Open Call, 50% of the budget will be provided to them beforehand. The rest of the amount will be handed to them after the successful completion of their experiment. Thus, there will not be a competitive award based on their performance, as was the case in the 1st Open Call. On the contrary, all selected SMEs will be guaranteed funding.

The selection process will be competitive and will rely on the following criteria: a) the applicant is eligible, b) the proposed experiment is feasible, and c) the proposed experiment is interesting for 5G-IANA and has an impact on the project.

The number of selected applications that will be given the funding is not known in advance, as was the case also for the first Open Call. As a rough approximation, and based on the experience from the 1st Open Call, we expect that a maximum of 5 SMEs' experiments can be accommodated, leading to a funding of **20000 euros to each one**.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Deliverable 6.3 has described the devised 5G-IANA engagement plan of the third party experimentation. The project has a strong focus towards promoting the impact that the AOEP platform can have on SMEs, and towards attracting such SMEs to be engaged in conducting validation experiments of use cases of their interest.

Based on the received applications during the first Open Call and their actual engagement following their selection, it has become apparent that engaging SMEs with limited funding options is a very challenging task, in the sense that some SMEs might lose their momentum, or prioritise other tasks that inevitably delay the experimentation on 5G-IANA platform.

As a countermeasure in view of the second project Open Call (to be launched in January 2023), we have increased the allocated funding. While in the first Open Call there was one award of 15000 euros to be offered to the best performing SME, the second Open Call will follow a funding scheme where all selected SMEs will be given budge beforehand.

This deliverable contains all the information with respect to the activities that involve third parties up to December 2023; however, the project will continue intensively its efforts on the second Open Call that will run within 2024.

APPENDIX 1: PROOF OF CONCEPT REPORT BY LINK ROBOTICS

Introduction

In this report, the experiments in Nokia Research Center, Ulm/Germany for the Link Robotics' prototype VINS-RTK are introduced in scope of a 5G-IANA Micro Project and the experimental results taken are discussed.

Figure 15: VINS-RTK mounted on the test vehicle

The VINS-RTK is a prototype which uses an Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU), a monocular camera and RTK-capable Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) receiver to calculate the position, orientation and velocity of the vehicle. It uses Multi-State Constraint Kalman Filter (MSCKF) and is capable of giving the real-time output at 10 Hz.

Service setup description

The service is a localization system for robots and autonomous/connected vehicles. It uses a monocular camera, inertial measurement unit (IMU) and RTK-capable (Real Time Kinematics) GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite System) receiver. Also, inside the enclosure, there is a 5G GSM modem from Simcom (SIM8200EA) connected to a custom interface card.

Hardware Components

A brief description of hardware components are as follows, as shown in Figure 16:

- **Camera**: For visual-inertial algorithm, a monocular camera is required to track the visual features and extract meaningful information about ego-motion of the vehicle/enclosure.
- **Inertial Measurement Unit**: For accurate and reliable localization, the combination of IMU and camera gives satisfying results with and without GNSS information. If it is used without GNSS or if the GNSS signal is poor, the IMU-camera combination will continue to give good localization information.

Figure 16: Hardware and Data Flow Diagram

- **RTK-GNSS Receiver**: Real Time Kinematics is a technique for improving the accuracy of GNSS output from meters to centimeters by using a ground station. Also, it is known as differential GPS. The technique can be used both by using a ground station and RF-modems and over Internet by using a subscription-based RTK service. In the project, RTK service used was Hexagon Smartnet Internet RTK service.

The receiver used in the enclosure is capable of working in both normal GNSS and RTK modes. It is assembled onto the interface card.

- Computation module: Nvidia Jetson Xavier NX computation module is used in the product enclosure for visual-inertial navigation algorithm. It outputs the current position of the vehicle at 10 Hz. The camera is connected to the Jetson carrier board over MIPI interface. Also, the RTK-GNSS and IMU devices are connected to a custom interface board. This interface board has an MPU System on Module (SoM) and custom interface software to maintain RTK navigation data. The IMU and RTK navigation data are sent to the Jetson over high speed UART port.

- 5G Interface card: The 5G interface card is connected to the Jetson hardware over UART, as explained in the computation module section. The interface card includes an STM32MP1 MPU SoM, 5G GSM modem from Simcom which is connected to the MPU over USB port, UART connection to IMU and a RTK-capable GNSS receiver from U-blox which is connected to the MPU over UART.

The main task of the 5G interface card is to get RTCM (Radio Technical Commission for Maritime Services) correction data over NTRIP protocol (Network Transport of RTCM over Internet Protocol) from Internet RTK servers over 5G GSM network and to send them to the GNSS receiver in order to obtain RTK corrected GNSS position data. After the GNSS data is come to the MPU, it is sent over the Jetson UART port to the Jetson hardware along with the IMU data.

Software Components

Also, the software components include the Computer Vision Software and Sensor Software which is the Network Application in the project. They can be summarized as follows:

- Computer Vision Software: The computer vision part includes a MSCKF (Multi-State Constraint Kalman Filter) to extract meaningful localization data by using camera and IMU along with RTK-GNSS sensors. The details of the algorithm are not explained here.

This part of the software stack is running on the Jetson hardware on Robot Operating System (ROS noetic). Also, there is an interface driver software running on ROS, which reads the communication UART port between Jetson and 5G interface card.

- Sensor Software (the Network Application): The sensor software is running on the MPU on the 5G interface card. It includes a custom GNSS driver which resolves NMEA protocol and sends the RTCM correction data to the host computer (Jetson hardware) and a custom IMU driver interfacing the IMU hardware.

The whole sensor software is capable of receiving the IMU data at 200Hz and the GNSS data at 4Hz simultaneously. Both data are sent over the UART.

For 5G-IANA project, the software would send also the position and orientation of the vehicle to the Nokia servers. Some other software connected to the Nokia servers can easily obtain the data and will be able to use the data for its own purposes. This part is still under development.

The Application Functions (AF) of the software are summarized above. The Network Function (NF) of the software can be explained here.

The main part of the software which takes the responsibility for network function (NF) is the Sensor Software. As explained briefly in the aforementioned section, it sends a NTRIP protocol request and waits for the answer from the Internet-RTK server over the 5G GSM network. After the response is received, the software starts receiving RTCM data from the Internet. When the connection is dropped, the software automatically tries to reconnect and resend the NTRIP request.

Traffic Flow

To mention about the Traffic Flow for the Sensor Software, there is mainly bi-directional traffic flow for NTRIP protocol. The software sends a request packet over IP which contains NMEA-GGA sentence and receives RTCM correction data.

- The content of the request packet: Host IP, NMEA-GGA sentence, authentication information (username and password given by the Internet RTK service)
- The content of the response packet: RTCM v3 correction data (depending on the service used the protocol version may change)

Scenario description

The experiments are done near the campus of University of Ulm where the 5G coverage of Nokia private GSM network is available.

Figure 17: Driven paths for the two experiments

For the two experiments to be explained, there are two driving paths near the University of Ulm given in Figure 17.

Pre-conditions

The pre-conditions were:

- The presence of the Internet RTK subscription: The RTK service bought from Hexagon is used.
- The presence of 5G private GSM network coverage: In some regions, there was no network coverage, which was a known issue. The private network of the Nokia with a sim card from Nokia is used.
- The weather conditions: The weather was rainy and cloudy which affected the GNSS signals slightly. As a result, some regions GNSS signal was poor and the RTK receiver was not giving the output at its best (1-2 cm). The possible reason for this issue is that because of cloudy weather, the satellite view was not perfect during the whole experiment.
- Compass angle: The compass angle is extracted at the start of the experiment from the IMU sensor but it can give a yaw offset because of the possible hard and soft iron magnetic field effects for the magnetometer. The software could automatically calibrate the IMU yaw angle and gave correct heading angles.
- Initial position: The initial position of the vehicle is taken from the GNSS measurements.
- Satellite Map service: The free map service from Google maps is used.

Various Steps for Experiments

The steps followed in the experiments are as follows:

- 1) Mounting the enclosure onto the vehicle by using vacuum suction cups

- 2) Connecting the cables (power, ethernet, GNSS and GSM antennas)
- 3) Powering on the device by using a Li-Po battery
- 4) After the device is powered up, the RTK service is checked.
- 5) Waiting for RTK service and GNSS to settle (might take about 15 minutes)
- 6) Opening up the Graphical User Interface (GUI) and checking the accuracy of the GNSS from covariance values (they should be below 10 centimeters)
- 7) Checking the camera image and adjusting the exposure according to the ambient light
- 8) Starting the main software and checking if the algorithm is running correctly
- 9) Opening up the ROS nodes necessary for debugging such as saving the data for future purposes
- 10) The device is ready for driving.

Validation/Evaluation Objectives

In the experiments, the validation/evaluation objectives are as follows:

- The performance of the sensor driver software:

- ◆ The driver software should run reliably and giving centimeter RTK-GNSS output accuracy (1-2 cm) at best.
- ◆ It should output GNSS data at 4Hz and IMU data at 200Hz.

- The performance of the VINS-RTK:

- ◆ The software should give reliable and instantaneous localization information.
- ◆ During RTK-fix, it should give a few centimeters of accuracy at best.
- ◆ During RTK-float or GNSS-fix, it should continue giving the correct localization.
- ◆ During dead-reckoning, it should continue giving relative localization with respect to the last position.
- ◆ The output rate should be 10Hz. The latency of the software should be about 50 ms average.

Metrics

The VINS-RTK software output should give 1-2 centimeters accuracy during RTK-fix depending on the environmental factors such as weather conditions, visible satellites and network coverage.

The cumulative error of the VINS-RTK should be below 1% when running with Internet RTK service even if the RTK is not available in some regions.

Assessment

The assessment of the product performance is done with two ground experiments. A van vehicle from Nokia was used. The enclosure is mounted onto the vehicle by using vacuum suction cups. Two cables for ethernet and power were used. There was a Li-po battery for powering the device.

Figure 18: Inside the test vehicle with ground station PC and VINS-RTK enclosure

In Figure 18, the product enclosure along with the ground station laptop are shown inside the test vehicle.

The software inside the enclosure is run while the vehicle is driving inside the pre-defined path. The vehicle is driven by a person from Nokia manually.

Figure 19: Test results for the experiment 1

In this section, two test results are given which are conducted near the university campus. Along the whole paths the 5G coverage was available except for some regions. In these regions, the RTK service cannot be reached, so the fix was only GNSS fix giving accuracy about 1 meter.

Within the 5G covered regions, the GNSS receiver was able to go into RTK mode which can give below meters accuracy depending on the factors such as satellites in view, the large buildings, trees etc. The RTK could perform about 1 centimeter accuracy at best.

In the regions with low quality GNSS coverage, e.g. no 5G coverage, the software could perform and continued giving the position-orientation information.

Figure 20: Test results for the experiment 2

In Figures 19 and 20, the two output trajectories of the software are given from two experiments.

The path length of the first experiment was about 4.3 kilometers. The accuracy was about 1 cm when RTK was available (at best). Also, the RMS error for the whole trajectory was measured as 0.75 meters including the regions with 5G outage (no RTK) compared to the GNSS output. It corresponds to 0.02% cumulative RMS error with respect to the distance travelled.

The path length of the second experiment was about 5.7 kilometers. The accuracy was about 1 cm when RTK was available (at best). Also, the RMS error for the whole trajectory was 2.84 meters including the regions with 5G outage (no RTK) compared to the GNSS output. It corresponds to 0.05% cumulative RMS error with respect to the distance travelled.

	Experiment #1	Experiment #2
Cumulative Error	0.02%	0.05%
Absolute Accuracy	1-2 cm with RTK-fix	1-2 cm with RTK-fix
Software Latency	~ 50 ms	~ 50 ms

Table 2: Evaluations

In Table 2, the evaluations of the results after the two experiments are summarized.

Figure 21: Connection test between the Nokia Server and ground station PC

In addition to the ground experiments, another test on the 5G network is performed. In this test, as shown in Figure 21, a connection between the ground station PC and Nokia server over the VPN is established. An example data -GPS coordinates at 10 Hz- is sent over the connection. On the Nokia server, a server running in docker image is receiving the data and publishing the data inside the ROS operating system at 10 Hz. This experiment demonstrates the scenario in which the VINS-RTK would send the position-orientation data over the 5G network to the Nokia server. On the server, the data could be stored in a database or published / sent to another software such as a Graphical User Interface (GUI) or used by a software on the 5G-IANA platform.

Feedback on the 5G-IANA platform

The localization of the vehicle is a crucial aspect especially in autonomous driving and vehicle tracking applications.

A possible use case is that the calculated output of the VINS-RTK can be stored on Nokia servers, or can be consumed real-time on the server according to the application. To achieve this goal, a TCP server software maintained on the docker environment can be integrated to the system. The VINS-RTK would send the estimation outputs over private network to the Nokia servers. Another software would connect to the Nokia servers, e.g. from a PC, and run a GUI or use the position/orientation information for its own purposes such as data collecting, analysing the travelled path or velocities. Also, it can be used on the vehicle computer as an input of another sensor fusion engine for autonomous driving to improve the quality of the localization.

Results and Future Works

According to the experimental results, the VINS-RTK can perform well real-time under hard conditions such as rain and 5G outage. It can give centimeter accuracy where the RTK service is available. Also, when RTK service is lost, it is able to continue its operation.

All in all, the hardware and software of the VINS system is verified on the real and hard conditions in Nokia Research Center at Ulm and successful results are obtained.

In future, the software will be extended to send the position and orientation of the vehicle to the Nokia servers while the vehicle is driving. Also, the prototype can be integrated into the navigation stack of a test vehicle for autonomous driving use cases.

Moreover, the prototype can be used as a vehicle tracking device which will send the position-orientation data to a server, e.g. Nokia servers. The data can be either stored in the server or used without being stored. Then, a software, e.g. a GUI, will query the data from the server and show the position/orientation of the vehicle on the screen. By this way, multiple vehicles can be tracked from a single node.

APPENDIX 2: 5G-IANA OPEN CALL INTEREST FORM

General information

- Name and Surname (of contact person)
- E-mail (of contact person)
- Is your organization characterized as an SME/start-up?
- Name of the organization
- Website of the organization
- Please provide a short description of your business (main activities, year of foundation, VAT number)
- What is the country of establishment?

Ambitions and development plans

- Describe the service/application or product that you plan to deploy in the 5G-IANA platform and the “use case/scenario” you would like to implement.
- Provide more details about the experiment that you would like to run on the 5G-IANA platform.
- What is the current stage of your product or service?
 - Idea phase
 - Under development
 - Demo
 - Prototype
 - Other: _____

Experience

- Do you have any prior experience with EU R&D projects?
- Have you already developed any Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) or network applications (nApps) to be utilized or are you planning to develop them? Provide more details:
- Do you have any experience with 5G technology?

Expectations from the platform

- Why do you deem 5G essential for your solution/product?

- How do you plan to integrate 5G into your solution/product?
- What are your expectations regarding 5G connectivity (round trip time, upload and download data rate, service reliability)? How are these associated with your experiment?
- What type of resources will be required from 5G-IANA to run your experiment? Provide rough estimates for the number of On-Board Units (OBUs), Road-Side Units (RSUs), vehicles, and amount of CPUs, RAM, storage, etc.
- How much time would you need to run your experiment (not including training, pre-testing activities and getting familiar with the platform functionalities)?
- Do you envision that AI/ML could provide added value to your experiment/service?

Expected impact

- What would the expected gain from experimentation with the 5G-IANA platform be?
 - Testing of an application using 5G
 - Developing a new product or service
 - Developing a new virtual network function / network application
 - Research purposes
 - Interest in the business model
 - Other: _____
- What is the expected outcome of the experimentation in the 5G-IANA platform for your business? Would you need business modelling guidance from 5G-IANA experts?
- What data do you plan to collect/generate during the experiment? Are you going to provide open access to them?

Before you submit

- How did you learn about the 5G-IANA Open Call?
- Please add any other comments you would like to accompany your application.

GDPR acknowledgement

All Open Call projects will be expected to comply with the General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR).

Do you agree: Y/N